

Gravimetric and Spectrophotometric Determination of Iridium (III) with Thiosalicylamide

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Thiosalicylamide is recommended for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of iridium (III). Iridium (III) is precipitated quantitatively with thiosalicylamide in hot acetate buffer of pH 4.6 to 5.8. The orange-yellow complex formed is ignited in a current of hydrogen and weighed as metal. Iridium (III) is determined in the presence of large number of base metals and is separated from platinum (IV), gold (III), palladium (II) or osmium (VI) by prior precipitation of the latter metal with thiosalicylamide. Rhodium (III) and ruthenium (III), however, interfere.

For spectrophotometric measurements the orange-yellow iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex is extracted with isobutylmethyl ketone-ethanol mixture from the acetate medium (pH 5.3-6.2). The yellow extract shows maximum absorbance at 400 nm and Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 1.84 to 9.20 $\mu\text{g Irml}^{-1}$ at the same wave length. The molar absorptivity of the complex is 1.06×10^4 . Among all the commonly associated base metals and noble metals, only rhodium (III) interferes.

VERY few analytical methods have been reported for the gravimetric determination of iridium. Beamish¹, recommended hydrolytic precipitation method² for the gravimetric estimation of the metal but the procedure involves interferences by the other noble metals. 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole³ is the only organic reagent which has been employed for the quantitative precipitation of iridium. The method is, however, suitable for small amounts of the metal. Tin (II) bromide⁴ was applied for the colorimetric determination of iridium, but the colour reaction suffered from excessive interferences and was very sensitive towards variations in experimental conditions. Mixed acid method introduced by Ayres and Quick⁵, is discouraged because of its poor precision. The other methods used for the photometric determination of iridium, in general, require a close control of the medium in which the colour is developed.

Thiosalicylamide has been used by Shome and co-workers⁶⁻⁸ for the determination of palladium, rhodium, ruthenium, platinum, osmium and gold. In the present investigation thiosalicylamide has been found to provide a simpler and quicker procedure for the determination of iridium (III) both in macro and micro quantities. The reagent forms an orange-yellow precipitate with iridium (III) at pH 4.6-5.8.

The iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex loses weight during the process of drying and hence unsuitable for direct weighing. Since the reaction is quantitative, the precipitate is ignited to metal for the determination of iridium. Iridium has been separated from commonly associated base metals and from the other noble metals (except rhodium and ruthenium) using thiosalicylamide as precipitant.

The orange-yellow precipitate formed by thiosalicylamide with iridium (III) can be extracted in isobutylmethyl ketone in presence of a few ml of ethanol; complete extraction of iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex takes place in the pH range 5.3 to 6.2. The yellow extract shows maximum absorbance at 400 nm, and follows Beer's law over the concentration range of 1.84 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 9.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of iridium at the same wave length. The interferences of platinum (IV), palladium (II), osmium (VI), gold (III) and ruthenium (III) can be avoided by the prior extraction of the metals with this reagent at higher acidities.

Experimental

Apparatus

A Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer, Model PMQ 11, with 1 cm quartz cells, was used for spectrophotometric measurements. A Cambridge pH Meter (Bench Model) equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements.

Standard iridium solution

Iridium (III) chloride (hydrated) was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and standardised by the hydrolytic precipitation method².

Diverse ion solutions

Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of pure compounds in distilled water. Dilute hydrochloric acid was used where required.

Reagent solutions

A 1% solution of thiosalicylamide in 10–15% ethanol was used for the precipitation of iridium. A 0.01M reagent solution was used for the spectrophotometric measurements.

All the chemicals used were of either A.R. or G.R. quality.

Gravimetric Determination of Iridium (III) :

Procedure : Dilute the metal ion solution to 125–150 ml and adjust its pH to 4.6–5.8 with 10% sodium acetate solution. Heat the solution to boiling and add 8–10 ml of 1% reagent per 10 mg of the metal. Boil the mixture with vigorous stirring for about half an hour, during which time iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex separates as a granular precipitate. Allow the mixture to stand for ca 3–6 hrs on a steam bath until the supernatant liquid is almost colourless. Filter through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper and wash with hot water. Transfer the precipitate to a porcelain crucible, dry slightly, char the paper, ignite at 650° in air and then in hydrogen, cool under hydrogen and weigh as metal. Typical results are shown in Table 1. The iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex begins to coagulate above pH 2.8, the optimum pH range for quantitative precipitation being 4.6–5.8.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRIDIUM(III)

Iridium taken (mg)	Iridium found (mg)	Error (mg)	Iridium taken (mg)	Iridium found (mg)	Error (mg)
8.50	8.48	−0.02	21.25	21.23	−0.02
8.50	8.47	−0.03	21.25	21.23	−0.02
17.00	16.99	−0.01	25.50	25.48	−0.02
17.00	16.97	−0.03	25.50	25.49	−0.01

Determination of iridium (III) in presence of base metals : Iridium (III) was determined with thiosalicylamide in a mixture containing known amounts of iridium (III) and Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Cu, Cd, Fe (III), Ga, In, Tl (as their chlorides), Al, Cr (as their sulphates), lead (as acetate), ammonium molybdate or uranyl acetate. The results are shown in Table 2.

Separation of iridium (III) from palladium (II), platinum (IV), gold (III) and osmium (VI) :

Iridium could be separated from palladium, platinum, gold, and osmium using thiosalicylamide as precipitant. Palladium, platinum and gold were first precipitated with thiosalicylamide from 3N hydrochloric acid medium and filtered. The filtrate was adjusted to pH 4.6–5.8 and iridium was subsequently determined with thiosalicylamide as before.

The mixture of osmium and iridium solutions was adjusted to pH 2.5, and osmium was first precipitated with thiosalicylamide in the cold. Iridium was then determined in the filtrate after adjusting its pH to 4.6–5.8 as before. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC SEPARATION OF IRIDIUM(III) FROM DIVERSE IONS

Ir taken (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Ir found (mg)	Ir taken (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Ir found (mg)
8.50	Co ²⁺ (50) ^a	8.49	8.50	Pd ²⁺ (11.8)	8.47
8.50	Ni ²⁺ (50) ^a	8.48	8.50	Pt ⁴⁺ (12.4)	8.48
8.50	Fe ³⁺ (20) ^a	8.48	8.50	Au ³⁺ (11.34)	8.48
8.50	Mn ²⁺ (50) ^a	8.49		Pd ²⁺ (11.8)	
8.50	Zn ²⁺ (50) ^a	8.48	8.50	Pt ⁴⁺ (12.4)	8.46
				Au ³⁺ (11.34)	
8.50	Mo ⁶⁺ (30) ^a	8.50			
8.50	Cu ²⁺ (10) ^b	8.49	17.00	Pd ²⁺ (11.8)	16.96
8.50	Al ³⁺ (50) ^a	8.51		Pt ⁴⁺ (12.4)	
				Au ³⁺ (11.3)	
8.50	Ga ³⁺ (20) ^a	8.48			
8.50	In ³⁺ (15) ^a	8.48	8.50	Os ⁶⁺ (9.50)	8.48
8.50	Tl ³⁺ (10) ^a	8.48	17.00	Os ⁶⁺ (9.50)	16.97
8.50	U ⁶⁺ (15) ^a	8.47			
8.50	Pb ²⁺ (50) ^b	8.46			

a = in presence of tartrate ions
b = in presence of EDTA.

Spectrophotometric determination of iridium (III) :

Procedure : Introduce a measured amount of iridium (III) solution containing 175–200 µg of the metal into a 100 ml separatory funnel, add 5 ml of 10% potassium chloride and adjust the acidity to pH 5.3–6.2 with 10% sodium acetate and dilute hydrochloric acid. Mix the solution thoroughly with 4 to 5 ml of an ethanolic 10^{−2}M solution of thiosalicylamide. Place the funnel with its content over a steam bath for about an hour. Cool to room temperature, add 10 ml of ethanol, and extract the complex 3–4 times with 5 ml portions of isobutylmethyl ketone. Collect the combined extracts in a 25 ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with isobutylmethyl ketone. Measure the absorbance at 400 nm against an appropriate blank prepared under the same conditions with the same quantity of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance Curves : The absorbance curves of the solutions of the iridium(III)-thiosalicylamide complex in isobutylmethyl ketone-ethanol mixture, are shown in Fig. 1. The curves show maximum absorption at 400 nm.

Effect of Variables : The acidity of the iridium (III) solution was adjusted with 10% sodium acetate solution and dilute hydrochloric acid. The pH values of the aqueous layers were measured after the extraction of the metal complex. It was observed that 100% extraction of the metal ion could be made at pH 5.3–6.2.

It was found that iridium (III) was completely extracted when the reagent concentration was 20 times the molar concentration of the metal ion.

The colour-of the extract was found to be stable for at least 6 hrs.

Effect of diverse ions : Iridium (III) could be determined in presence of appreciable amounts of

Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex in isobutyl methylketone-ethanol mixture. [Ir] : (●) 7.36 µg/ml; (Δ) 5.52 µg/ml; (○) 3.68 µg/ml.

diverse ions following the above procedure. The tolerance limits (*i.e.* concentrations causing an error less than 2%) are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRIDIUM (III)

Iridium taken (176.2 µg), pH = 5.6

Diverse ion	Amount tolerated (µg)	Diverse ion	Amount tolerated (µg)
Co ²⁺	1200 ^a	UO ₂ ²⁺	500 ^a
Ni ²⁺	1200 ^a	Mo ⁶⁺	1200 ^a
Mn ²⁺	1200 ^a	Pb ²⁺	5000 ^b
Zn ²⁺	1500 ^a	Pt ⁴⁺	260
Cd ²⁺	1000 ^a	Pd ²⁺	125
Fe ³⁺	200 ^a	Au ³⁺	140
Al ³⁺	1000 ^a	Ru ³⁺	140
Cr ³⁺	1000 ^a	Os ⁶⁺	150
Ga ³⁺	500 ^a	Cu ²⁺	400 ^b
In ³⁺	500 ^a	Rh ³⁺	interferes
Tl ³⁺	400 ^a		

^a = in presence of tartrate ions
^b = in presence of EDTA.

Nature of the complex : The empirical formula of the iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex was determined by the mole ratio method¹⁰. The results in Fig. 2. clearly indicate that the metal to reagent ratio in the complex is 1 : 3. This ratio was further confirmed by the conventional slope ratio method.

Dissociation constant of the complex : The degree of dissociation (α) was calculated according to the following equation¹¹.

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

where E_m = Absorbance of the metal-chelate extract in presence of excess reagent.

Fig. 2. Composition by mole ratio method applied to iridium (III)-thiosalicylamide complex.

E_s = Absorbance at mole ratio 1 : 3 (from Fig. 2).

Metal ion concentration $3.68 \times 10^{-5} M$.

From the value of the degree of dissociation, the dissociation constant was calculated and found to be 6.24×10^{-15} .

Molar absorptivity, sensitivity, precision and accuracy : Molar absorptivity of the complex, sensitivity, of the colour reaction, coefficient of variation and relative mean error for the determination are 1.06×10^4 , $0.018 \mu g/cm^2$, 0.45% and 0.21% respectively.

References

1. F. E. BEAMISH, *The Analytical Chemistry of the Noble Metals*. Pergamon Press Inc., London, 1966, p. 277.
2. M. A. HILL and F. E. BEAMISH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 590.
3. R. R. BAREFOOT, W. J. McDONNELL and F. E. BEAMISH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 514.
4. S. S. BERMAN and W. A. E. MCBRYDE, *Analyst.*, 1956, **81**, 566.
5. G. H. AYRES and QUICK, *Anal. Chim.*, 1950, **22**, 1403.
6. K. SUR and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **48**, 145.
7. K. SUR and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **57**, 201.
8. K. SUR, M. MAZUMDAR and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **59**, 306.
9. A. S. MEYER and G. H. AYRES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 49.
10. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.